

IMIA WG Language and Meaning in BioMedicine

Report for the Year July 2017 – June 2018

Date: July 1st, 2018

Website of the WG:

<http://imia-medinfo.org/wp/language-and-meaning-in-biomedicine/>

<https://imiawg6lamb.wordpress.com/>

LinkedIn of the WG:

<https://www.linkedin.com/groups/3680642>

Chair (2015-20xx)

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1. **Background** – IMIA's WG Language and Meaning in Biomedicine (formerly known as the Medical Concept Representation Working Group up to 2014) is an international forum for state-of-the-art dialogue and collaboration on semantics in healthcare and biomedical research, encompassing language, biomedical terminologies and ontologies. Since its formation, the working group was charged with: (1) Reviewing health data terminology and

classification needs for the world community; (2) Evaluating information processing technology in meeting these defined needs; and (3) Recommending methods for future terminology systems.

2. Achievement

- a.** Medinfo 2017: Co-organization and presentation in Workshop “Unstructured Clinical Data Reuse for Precision Medicine: Current Status and Future Progress”
- b.** Business meeting held Medinfo 2017.
- c.** Contribution to IMIA Yearbook 2018 – “Recent developments in clinical terminologies – SNOMED CT, LOINC and RxNorm”

- 3. Participation** – As described above, the Working Group participated in activities at Medinfo 2017 in Hangzhou, and contributed to the IMIA Yearbook.
- 4. Outreach** – We have shared our previous report in the LinkedIn group and on the wordpress site.
- 5. Collaboration** – Discussions with the EFMI board and council have been held after their termination of the Natural Language Understanding working group. European members of the LaMB WG are likely to be involved in a reinstatement of this European working group.